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M7 Agricultural Biodiversity Surveys and Workshops

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Context and partners

The WorldFAIR project Case Study on Agricultural Biodiversity (project Work Package 10) is dedicated to plant-pollinator interaction data and was born within the Research Data Alliance (RDA) 'Improving Global Agricultural Data Community of Practice' (IGAD)¹. The team is led by Embrapa (Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation)² and gathers several initiatives and institutions, namely the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) Biological Interaction Data Interest Group³, and the other four direct beneficiaries institutions: Meise Botanic Garden, HiveTracks, Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization (KALRO) and the RDA Association; plus a large network of organisations contributing in-kind and not receiving funding, such as the University de São Paulo (Brazil), University of Campinas (Brazil), USDA Agricultural Research Service and Natural Resources Conservation Service (USA), Agriculture and Agri-food Canada (AAFC - Canada), Federal University of São Carlos (Brazil), University of Buenos Aires, Global Biotic Interactions (GloBI), and the UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology (UKCEH).

IGAD has identified initiatives related to plant-pollinator data standardisation being carried out by different groups within the community, and assembled a representative team to collaborate on enabling FAIR data for this key ecosystem service that is vital for agriculture and many other mechanisms that sustain life on Earth.

Building links: initial communication, discovery and collaboration activities

In anticipation of the WorldFAIR project, and during the first year of the project, the WP10 Agricultural Biodiversity Case Study surveyed the community in a number of ways in order to identify plant pollination use cases. One approach was to participate in relevant meetings and to promote events to raise awareness about the Case Study and encourage collaboration, and the other was a team effort to search for data sources available online, good practices and standards.

The first activity towards collecting and documenting agriculture-specific plant-pollination use cases occurred in anticipation of the official kick-off of the WorldFAIR project⁴, during the Improving Global Agricultural Data (IGAD) Community of Practice Second Annual Virtual Meeting held on 29 March 2022. Debora Drucker (WP lead, Embrapa) and Abram Bicksler of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) organised a ninety-minute session on plant-pollinator interactions data standards with five presentations of initiatives dealing with plant-pollinator

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/igad-community-practice>

² <https://www.embrapa.br/en/international>

³ <https://www.tdwg.org/community/interaction/>

⁴ WorldFAIR began officially in June 2022 - see <https://zenodo.org/record/6783620>

interactions from WorldFAIR WP10 collaborators, and a virtual discussion at “The Hive (FAO Pollinators)” virtual environment⁵; these activities provided a ‘warm up’ period for the WP team before the official start of the project activity.

The five initiatives presented at the March event were selected from submissions to an open call for presentations led by IGAD and initiatives previously unknown to the WP10 team were discovered with this event. Debora Drucker briefly presented the WorldFAIR project and this opportunity helped raise awareness about the Case Study and its specific scope. A recording is available on the RDA YouTube channel at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8FyTti3z9Dc>.

Another significant event occurred in June 2022 when the WP10 team organised a session at International Data Week (IDW). The session is described in detail here: <https://www.scidatacon.org/IDW-2022/sessions/418/>⁶. The session started with Prof. Jeff Ollerton’s overview entitled “Representing pollinators and pollination in large data sets: how deep do we want to go?” and was followed by presentations from WP10 partners who had submitted abstracts and presented their work, as follows:

1. Using gender-responsive technology development of a mobile app for beekeepers to increase standardised data uptake on plant-pollinator interactions - lessons learned from Ethiopia, Lebanon, and Uzbekistan (Max Rünzel - HiveTracks);
2. Experiences in the generation, utilisation and sharing of plant-pollinator interaction data, in Kenya (Muo Kasina - KALRO);
3. Challenges and opportunities of standardising plant-pollinator interactions (Maarten Trekels - Meise Botanic Garden);
4. On standardisation of plant-pollinators interactions data (José Augusto Salim - USP).

The Agricultural Biodiversity Case Study was also presented at the session ‘WorldFAIR – Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice – General Introduction’, described here: <https://www.scidatacon.org/IDW-2022/sessions/439/>.

Those two sessions at IDW contributed to increasing awareness about the Case Study activities and the recordings were made freely available and were shared with IGAD communities and networks, helping to reach relevant audiences and allowing for discovering new use cases that were

⁵ Described at

<https://www.fao.org/in-action/building-capacity-environmental-agreements/global/protect-pollinators-from-pesticides/pollinator-seminar/the-hive/en/>

⁶ Link to presentations and materials from the session:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1NUWE3Dq6nldt45sD8XUM8fKCX2Yqn5ii?usp=sharing>. Link to the session recording: <https://vimeo.com/743689216>.

documented and analysed in Task 10.1.

It is also worth highlighting a talk entitled “Representing pollinators and pollination in large data sets: an introduction to the new WorldFAIR project” which was delivered by Prof. Jeff Ollerton at the Scandinavian Association for Pollination Ecology (SCAPE)⁷ conference in October 2022. SCAPE is the world’s oldest and longest-running annual conference devoted to pollinators and pollination and has been held every year since 1987. The conference was attended by over 80 participants from around the world.

In addition, the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG), a community-based organisation dedicated to developing, ratifying, and promoting standards and guidelines for biodiversity data, has held an annual conference since 1985 and the WP10 lead presented WorldFAIR as a keynote presentation at this meeting in October 2022 (Drucker et al., 2022).

In 2023, two events contributed to publicising WP10 activities and collecting more use cases: the Case Study presentation at the IGAD session⁸ during the 20th RDA Plenary Meeting, and the Case Study presentation⁹ at the UNESCO Symposium “Towards a FAIRer World”¹⁰. Both of them occurred in March 2023. Finally, the main findings of the discovery phase of WP10 were presented in August 2023, “The WorldFAIR Case Study on Plant-pollinator Interactions”, during the RDA 10th Anniversary series of events¹¹.

Workshops

A series of workshops were also conducted in order to collect and document agriculture-specific plant-pollination use cases. The WP10 team participated in the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) workshop that was held in August 2022 for all WorldFAIR work packages, and developed the FIP for Plant-Pollinator Data, which was presented at the ‘FIPs - what have we learnt?’ workshop¹² in October 2022. This effort was crucial to direct the work planned for plant-pollinator interaction data FAIRness.

Another relevant workshop took place in Buenos Aires, Argentina, in November 2022 with the

⁷ <https://scape-pollination.org>

⁸ <https://youtu.be/eaYPQL0DJfA?si=tsX0-2bSk4cnKW3n>

⁹ Link to the recording: <https://vimeo.com/818708811>

¹⁰ <https://codata.org/events/science-and-policy-workshops/towards-a-fairer-world/>

¹¹ Described at

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries-events/events/%E2%80%98decade-data%E2%80%99-celebrating-10-years-rda/ras-10th-anniversary-events-and>

¹² <https://codata.org/events/conferences/fair-convergence-symposium-2022/fips-in-worldfair-what-have-we-learnt/>

SURPASS¹³ team ('Safeguarding Pollination Services in a Changing World: Theory into Practice'). One of the use case pilots of the next phase of the project is being held together with partners of this initiative.

The US National Native Bee Monitoring Research Coordination Network (RCN)¹⁴ held a workshop on data management in March 2023. WP10 activities were presented by Maarten Treckels¹⁵, Task 10.1 leader. He also participated in the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) workshop, 'Unified data model for mobilising and sharing collections data' at the annual meeting of the Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections (SPNHC).

All the presentations and workshops described here allowed the team to reach wider audiences and survey the community to discover plant-pollinator interaction datasets and use cases that were included in our analysis.

Agriculture-specific plant-pollination use cases collected and documented

The team effort dedicated to collecting and documenting agriculture-specific plant-pollination use cases started at the kick-off meeting for the Case Study that was held with beneficiaries and in-kind partners from several initiatives and organisations in July 2022. Data sources were collected from a big data search conducted on the Dimensions, Zenodo, Dryad, Figshare and DataOne portals, as well as by talking to the different stakeholders identified through the communication and discovery activities listed above. For the data sources available online, the strategy was to develop a script that could analyse the FAIRness of these sources with respect to the FAIR principles. This strategy was based on the efforts of the FAIR Implementation Profiles and presented in WorldFAIR Deliverable 10.1 (Treckels et al., 2023).

HiveTracks, a US-based startup that works with small-holder beekeepers to crowdsource environmental data, has contributed towards the goal of assessing the FAIRness of currently available plant-pollinator interaction datasets by mapping the relevant metadata of 29 datasets. In addition, by launching a new mobile and web app for beekeepers in Q1 2023, it laid the groundwork for collecting standardised plant-pollinator interaction data during the pilot phase.

Early in the WorldFAIR project, KALRO surveyed available literature on plant pollination studies in the African continent and extracted data from papers and supplementary files. They then standardised the data to the GloBI template, which is a widely-used data platform for biotic

¹³ <https://bee-surpass.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.nativebeemonitoring.org/>

¹⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e6ri5Gn87ZE>

interactions. This data was then examined by the WP partners and the results of these documentation and mapping activities were presented in Deliverable 10.1, 'Agriculture-related pollinator data standards use cases report' (Trekels et al., 2023).

Next steps

Advancing the biotic interactions module¹⁶ of the GBIF Unified Data Model (Miller et al., 2023) is part of the activities foreseen for WorldFAIR Tasks 10.2 and 10.3. Contributing to the Cross Domain Interoperability Framework¹⁷ with data from plant-pollinator interactions is also an ongoing activity. The analysis of the use cases will provide an essential indicator of the common data structures used within the discipline and how they relate to the representation of information from other disciplines.

WP10 will continue to promote the activities and present and discuss results with relevant audiences in the next phase of WorldFAIR, with the ultimate goal of promoting standards adoption and adherence to the FAIR principles, aligned with the next proposed deliverables D10.2 'Agricultural Biodiversity Standards, Best Practice and Guidelines Recommendations', and D10.3 'Agricultural Biodiversity FAIR data assessment rubrics'.

¹⁶

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1jzb54GbAkB_TOFljWof5BW6gn1ujSnXXJQu6aZgFAB4/edit#heading=h.25ixp1kek_b88

¹⁷ <https://worldfair-project.eu/cross-domain-interoperability-framework/>

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